

EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

WNoDES: SYSTEM ADMINISTRATION GUIDE INSTALLATION AND CONFIGURATION

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WNoDeS: System Administration Guide

Installation and Configuration

Date: March 7, 2013

TITLE:

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CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	6
2	WNODES COMPONENTS	7
2.1	OVERVIEW OF WNODES DEPLOYMENTS	8
3	QUICK START GUIDE	11
3.1	TORQUE/MAUI BATCH SYSTEM WITH MIXED MODE ENABLED	11
3.1.1	ON TORQUE SERVER	11
3.1.2	WNODES CORE SERVICES IN A STANDALONE DEPLOYMENT ON A SINGLE HOST	14
3.1.3	WORKER NODE ON A GIVEN IMAGE	21
3.2	WNODES OCCI SERVER	25
3.3	WNODES CACHEMANAGER SERVICE	28
4	INSTALLATION PREREQUISITES	34
4.1	OPERATING SYSTEM	34
4.2	DNS	34
4.3	DHCP	34
4.4	KVM	34
4.5	REPOSITORY DISTRIBUTION	34
4.6	IMAGE	34
4.7	BATCH SYSTEM	34
4.8	CERTIFICATES	34
4.8.1	OCCI SERVER	35
4.9	PUB KEY	35
5	WNODES INSTALLATION RECOMMENDATIONS	36
5.1	WNODES_NAMESERVER	36
5.2	WNODES_MANAGER	36
5.3	WNODES_HYPERVISOR	36
5.4	WNODES_BAIT	36
5.5	WNODES_SITE_SPECIFIC	37
5.6	WNODES OCCI SERVER	37
6	NAMESERVER CONFIGURATION	38
6.1	WNODES NAMESERVER MAC LIST FILE	38
6.2	WNODES HYPERVISOR FILE	39
6.3	WNODES BAIT FILE	40
6.4	WNODES NAMESERVER STATE	43

7	MANAGER CONFIGURATION	44
7.1	OPTIONS TO HANDLE VIRTUAL MACHINE IMAGES	44
7.2	OPTIONS TO OBTAIN VLANS INFORMATION	45
7.3	OPTIONS TO MODIFY THE REGISTERED HOSTNAMES	45
7.4	OPTIONS TO MANAGE THE CONFIGURATION FILES OF THE WNODES_BAIT AND WNODES_HYPERVISOR SERVICES	46
7.5	OPTIONS TO MANAGE THE WNODES_BAIT AND WNODES_HYPERVISOR STATUS	46
8	HYPERVERSOR CONFIGURATION	48
8.1	WNODES_HYPERVISOR_CONF	48
9	BAIT CONFIGURATION	49
9.1	WNODES_BAIT_CONF	49
10	BATCH SYSTEM CONFIGURATION	50
10.1	LSF	50
10.1.1	LSF_CLUSTER_FILE	50
10.1.2	LSF_BATCH_SITE_HOSTS_FILE	51
10.1.3	LSF_BATCH_SITE_QUEUES_FILE	51
10.2	TORQUE/MAUI	52
10.2.1	NODES_FILE	52
10.2.2	MAUI_FILE	53
10.2.3	CREATE_A_QUEUE	53
10.2.4	MODIFY_JOB_MANAGEMENT	54
10.2.5	REFRESH_QUEUE	54
11	SITE SPECIFIC CONFIGURATION	55
12	OCCI SERVER CONFIGURATION	58
12.1	WNODES_CLOUD_SETTINGS	58
12.2	RESOURCES MANAGEMENT	59
12.2.1	VIRTUAL MACHINES PRE-DEFINED SIZES	59
12.2.2	OCCI OPERATIONS	59
12.2.3	VM CREATION	59
12.2.4	VM STATUSES	60
12.2.5	VM DELETION	60
12.2.6	USER CREDENTIALS	60
12.2.7	EXAMPLES OF USAGE	60
12.2.8	WNODES_OCCI_API_REFERENCE_PAGE	61
12.2.9	LOG FILE	61

13 CACHEMANAGER CONFIGURATION	62
14 ACCOUNTING CONFIGURATION	64
15 WNODES PROCESSES	65
15.1 WNODES_NAMESERVER	65
15.2 WNODES_HYPERVISOR	65
15.3 WNODES_BAIT	66
15.4 WNODES_MANAGER	67

1 INTRODUCTION

This document provides useful information about the WNoDeS installation and configuration.

2 WNoDES COMPONENTS

WNoDeS is characterized by the following components (as shown in Figure 1):

Mandatory components: bait, hypervisor, manager, nameserver and site-specific.

Cloud components: Web/CLI and cachemanager

Figure 1: The overall WNoDeS components.

This version of WNoDeS supports an important feature called *mixed mode* that allows a computing farm to use the same physical worker node to execute both real jobs and virtual jobs. Table 1 sums up the pros and cons of enabling mixed mode feature.

Table 1: List of Pros and Cons

Pros	Cons
Increase the flexibility of the configuration of a farm	In case of LSF, increase the number of LSF licenses needed
Allow system administrators to progressively integrate WNoDeS into existing data centers	Add one more configuration step to execute standard real job in the system when the queue supports WNoDeS
Optimize the resource usage	
Allow jobs that require full performance to be executed on physical systems.	
Allow jobs that require hardware that is not easily virtualized to be executed on physical systems.	

Looking at Figure 1 from the top to the bottom:

Web/CLI provides compliance with the OCCI 1.1 specification and resources provisioning via a CLI or simple HTTP methods. Can be used to provide self-instantiation of virtual machines by local users;

Chachemanager takes care of Cloud resources provisioning; speeds up the allocation of virtual machines; keeps a cache of ready-to-use virtual machines, matches them to user requirements and makes them readily available for consumption;

Site-Specific can be considered as the site configuration resolver. It is the component that sends the resource request to the `wnodes_bait` service and checks the job status;

Accounting provides information on the resources that are used by a subject: cpu cores, bandwidth, ram and disk space;

Bait is the host resource manager responsible for verifying that there are resources to execute both real jobs and virtual jobs, requiring the instantiation of the virtual machine when necessary, and executing the job on the suitable resource;

Hypervisor is mainly the interface to the virtualization system responsible for instantiating virtual machines where the virtual job will be executed. However, if the mixed mode feature is enabled, it is also able to run real job;

Nameserver, Manager can be considered as the information management. The nameserver is a sort of catalogue responsible for keeping trace of all the virtual machines currently running for each hypervisor, and all the virtual machine images stored in the configured repository (see Section 4). The `Manager` is a Command Line Interface (CLI) that is responsible for the configuration of the repository of the virtual machine images. It provides a set of options to handle images, VLANs, hostnames, bait and hypervisor configuration files. Furthermore, it supports a set of options that manage bait and hypervisor status.

2.1 OVERVIEW OF WNODES DEPLOYMENTS

WNoDeS can be differently deployed on a given site in relation to its needs. However, both physical and virtual machines need to be prepared.

Figure 2 shows the WNoDeS deployment with the mixed mode feature disabled. In this case at least two hosts are necessary: one dedicated host is to install and configure the `wnodes_nameserver` service; and another one is to install and configure the `wnodes_hypervisor` service that will instantiate a virtual machine with the `wnodes_bait` service.

Figure 3 shows the WNoDeS deployment with the mixed mode enabled. In this case the `wnodes_bait` service is installed and configured on the same host of the `wnodes_hypervisor` service.

In both cases the batch system needs to be installed and configured.

Figure 4 shows the WNoDeS deployment with the mixed mode enabled and the cloud part. In this case at least four hosts are necessary: one dedicated host is to install and configure the `wnodes_nameserver` service; another one is to install and configure the `wnodes_hypervisor` service that will instantiate a virtual machine with the `wnodes_bait` service; the third one is to install and configure the `wnodes_cachemanager` service; and the last one is to install and configure the OCCI server. However, the `wnodes_cachemanager` service can stay on one of the other hosts.

Figure 2: The WNoDeS deployment without supporting mixed mode feature.

Figure 3: The WNoDeS deployment supporting mixed mode feature.

Figure 4: The WNoDeS deployment supporting cloud feature but without mixed mode feature.

3 QUICK START GUIDE

This guide gives the steps to be followed when installing the WNoDeS services in a given deployment.

3.1 TORQUE/MAUI BATCH SYSTEM WITH MIXED MODE ENABLED

Let us installing the WNoDeS services with mixed moded enabled and Torque/Maui as Batch System. Prepare at least two MAC-Addresses (e.g., MAC-1, MAC-2) and associated hostnames (e.g., test-1.cnaf.infn.it, test-2.cnaf.infn.it) for virtual machines, and configure a Torque/Maui server (also with a CE when necessary).

3.1.1 ON TORQUE SERVER

1. Disable iptables service:

```
# iptables -F
# chkconfig iptables off
# service iptables stop
```

2. Disable selinux

3. Create and setting a `qwnodes` queue on the Torque server (more details at [10.2.3](#))

- Edit a file called for example `wnodes_queue_command` in order to create and set a `qwnodes` queue. Below an example is shown.

```
# cat /root/wnodes_queue_command
create queue qwnodes
set queue qwnodes queue_type = Execution
set queue qwnodes Priority = 1000000
set queue qwnodes max_running = 80
set queue qwnodes resources_max.cput = 100:00:00
set queue qwnodes resources_max.walltime = 100:00:00
set queue qwnodes resources_default.neednodes = wnodes
set queue qwnodes enabled = True
set queue qwnodes started = True
```

- Run the `qmgr` command with the file specified above as input

```
# qmgr < /root/wnodes_queue_command
```

whose output is specified below:

```
Max open servers: 9
create queue qwnodes
set queue qwnodes queue_type = Execution
set queue qwnodes Priority = 1000000
set queue qwnodes max_running = 80
```

```
set queue qwnodes resources_max.cput = 100:00:00
set queue qwnodes resources_max.walltime = 100:00:00
set queue qwnodes resources_default.neednodes = wnodes
set queue qwnodes enabled = True
set queue qwnodes started = True
```

4. Modify Torque configuration (more details at [10.2.4](#))

- Configure the Torque server to allow job management from the `wnodes_preexec` service on the `wnodes_bait` host machine

```
# qmgr -c "set server managers +=root@<hostname>.<domain>"
```

where `<hostname>` is the hostname of the real machine where the `wnodes_bait` service runs. For each hostname where the `wnodes_bait` service runs executes the above command.

- Configure the Torque server to allow real job to use only the other queues

```
# qmgr -c "set queue demo resources_default.neednodes = lcgpro"
```

5. Add in the nodes configuration file the new nodes that WNoDeS will use to instantiate virtual machines (more details at [10.2.1](#)). Below an example is shown.

- on `sl5`

```
# cat /var/torque/server_priv/nodes
<other hostname>.<domain> np=2 lcgpro
<bait hostname 1>.<domain> np=3 wnodes bait
<virtual machine hostname 1>.<domain> np=1 <virtual machine hostname 1>
```

- on `sl6`

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/server_priv/nodes
<other hostname>.<domain> np=2 lcgpro
<bait hostname 1>.<domain> np=3 wnodes bait
<virtual machine hostname 1>.<domain> np=1 <virtual machine hostname 1>
```

For each hostname where the `wnodes_bait` service runs modifies the above file adding an entry as follows:

```
# <bait hostname x>.<domain> np=3 wnodes bait
```

where `x` goes from 1 to `N` with `N > 1`.

6. Restart the batch server

```
# service pbs_server restart
```

7. Configure maui to create a partition (more details at [10.2.2](#)).

- Edit file `maui.cfg`. Below an example is shown.

```
# cat /var/spool/maui/maui.cfg
## MAUI configuration example
SERVERHOST          emi-demo13.cnaf.infn.it
...

## Set PBS server polling interval. If you have short
## queues or/and jobs it is worth to set a short
## interval. (10 seconds)
...

## a max. 10 MByte log file in a logical location
...

## Set the delay to 1 minute before Maui tries to run a job again,
## in case it failed to run the first time.
## The default value is 1 hour.
...

NODECFG[<bait hostname 1>] PARTITION=virtual
CLASSCFG[qwnodes] PLIST=virtual PDEF=virtual
```

where `emi-demo13` is the hostname of the Torque server, and `<bait hostname 1>` is the hostname of the real machine where the `wnodes_bait` service runs. For each hostname where the `wnodes_bait` service runs modifies the above file adding an entry as follows:

```
# NODECFG[<bait hostname x>] PARTITION=virtual
```

where `x` goes from 1 to `N` with `N > 1`.

- Restart maui service

```
# service maui restart
```

8. Refresh queue (more details at [10.2.5](#))

9. Enable ssh without password

```
# cat /etc/ssh/sshd_config
...
HostbasedAuthentication yes
IgnoreUserKnownHosts yes
IgnoreRhosts yes
# service ssh restart
```

```
# cat /etc/ssh/shosts.equiv
...
<hostname worker node>.<domain>
<hostname wnodes>.<domain>
# cat /etc/ssh/ssh_known_hosts
...
worker node public key
wnodes public key
```

3.1.2 WNoDES CORE SERVICES IN A STANDALONE DEPLOYMENT ON A SINGLE HOST

1. Install one of the supported Operating System: SL5 64 bit, SL6 64 bit
2. Disable iptables service:

```
# iptables -F
# chkconfig iptables off
# service iptables stop
```

3. Disable selinux
4. Check hardware virtualization turned on in the BIOS:

```
# cat /proc/cpuinfo | egrep '(svm|vmx)'
```

5. Check the 'kvm' kernel module loaded.

```
# lsmod | grep kvm
```

If no, please run first

```
sudo modprobe kvm_intel
```

6. Not configure bridge
7. Not require host certificate
8. Satisfy common repository settings:

- on sl5

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/5/x86_64/
epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm
```

- on sl6

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/6/x86_64/epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm
```

9. Satisfy EMI repository settings:

- on sl5

```
# wget http://emisoft.web.cern.ch/emisoft/dist/EMI/3/sl5/x86_64/base/emi-release-3.0.0-1.el5.noarch.rpm
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck emi-release-3.0.0-1.el6.noarch.rpm
```

- on sl6

```
# wget http://emisoft.web.cern.ch/emisoft/dist/EMI/3/sl6/x86_64/base/emi-release-3.0.0-1.el6.noarch.rpm
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck emi-release-3.0.0-1.el6.noarch.rpm
```

10. Satisfy EGI repository settings to install EMI Worker Node

```
# wget http://repository.egi.eu/software/production/cas/1/current/repo-files/EGI-trustanchors.repo -O /etc/yum.repos.d/EGI-trustanchors.repo
```

11. Clean YUM cache

```
# yum clean all
# yum makecache
```

12. Install KVM

- on sl5

```
# yum install kvm-qemu-img
# yum install kmod-kvm
# yum install libvirt
# yum install python-virtinst
# yum install pyOpenSSL
# yum install virt-manager
```

- on sl6

```
# yum install qemu-kvm
# yum install libvirt
# yum install python-virtinst
# yum install pyOpenSSL
# yum install virt-manager
```

13. Enable libvirt

```
# chkconfig libvirtd on
# service libvirtd start
```

14. Install Torque/Maui client

- with EMI configuration

```
# yum install ca-policy-egi-core
# yum install lcg-CA
# yum install emi-wn emi-torque-client
```

- without EMI configuration

```
# yum install torque-client torque-mom
```

15. Install WNoDeS with Mixed Mode enabled

```
# yum install wnodes_utils wnodes_bait wnodes_hypervisor \
wnodes_manager wnodes_nameserver wnodes_site_specific
```

16. Configure the Torque/Maui client

- on the client host
 - with EMI configuration

(a) Edit def file

```
# cat site-info.def
CE_HOST=emi-demo13.$MY_DOMAIN
CE_SMP_SIZE=2
BATCH_SERVER=$CE_HOST

JOB_MANAGER=pbs
CE_BATCH_SYS=pbs
BATCH_BIN_DIR=/usr/bin
BATCH_VERSION=torque-<version>
BATCH_LOG_DIR=/var/torque
BATCH_CONF_DIR=/opt/
```

(b) Run yaim

```
# /opt/glite/yaim/bin/yaim -v -c -s site-info.def
-n WN -n TORQUE_client
```

(c) Verify munge key

```
# chown munge /etc/munge/munge.key
# ll /etc/munge/munge.key
-r----- 1 munge root 1024 Mar 15 17:47 /etc/munge/munge.key
```

(d) Enable munge service

```
# chkconfig munge on
# service munge start
```

– without EMI configuration

(a) Create node file

* on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/mom_priv/config
$pbsserver <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$restricted <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$logevent 255
$ideal_load 2.5
$max_load 2.4
```

* on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/mom_priv/config
$pbsserver <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$restricted <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$logevent 255
$ideal_load 2.5
$max_load 2.4
```

(b) Enable pbs_mom service

```
# chkconfig pbs_mom on
# service pbs_mom restart
```

(c) Get the munge.key file from the Torque server host and copy it in /etc/munge/

(d) Verify munge key

```
# chown munge /etc/munge/munge.key
# ll /etc/munge/munge.key
-r----- 1 munge root 1024 Mar 15 17:47 /etc/munge/munge.key
```

(e) Enable munge server

```
# chkconfig munge on
# service munge start
```

(f) Set torque hostname server

* on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/server_name
<hostname torque>.<domain>
```

* on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/server_name  
<hostname torque>.<domain>
```

- on the server host

- (a) Add the new host that contains the `wnodes_bait` service to the `nodes` file

- on `sl5`

```
# cat /var/torque/server_priv/nodes  
<hostname>.<domain> np=4 wnodes bait  
...
```

- on `sl6`

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/server_priv/nodes  
<hostname>.<domain> np=4 wnodes bait  
...
```

- (b) Restart `pbs_server` server

```
# service pbs_server start
```

- (c) Add the new host that contains the `wnodes_bait` service to the `maui` file

```
# cat /var/spool/maui/maui.cfg  
...  
CLASSCFG[wnodes]          PLIST=virtual PDEF=virtual  
NODECFG[<hostname>.<domain>] PARITION=virtual
```

- (d) Restart `maui` server

```
# service maui start
```

17. Enable ssh without password

```
# cat /etc/ssh/ssh_config  
...  
PasswordAuthentication yes  
EnableSSHKeySign yes  
HostbasedAuthentication yes  
StrictHostKeyChecking no
```

18. Configure the `wnodes_preexec` service

```
# chmod 500 /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec  
# cp /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf.tpl  
  /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf  
# cat /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf  
[general]  
TMPFILE=/tmp/my_bait  
LOCAL_DOMAIN =<domain>
```

```
NS_HOST=<hostname nameserver>.<domain>
NS_PORT=8219
BAIT_PORT=8111
FAIL_RETURN_STATUS=3
```

```
[default]
TYPE=BATCH_REAL
IMG=wnodes_tf_wn
NETWORK_TYPE=OPEN
CPU=1
MEM=2500
STORAGE=30
ENABLEVIRTIO=YES
BANDWIDTH=10
PX_SCRIPT=
```

- on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/mom_priv/prologue
#!/bin/bash

while [ ! -f /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec ];
do sleep 3 ;
done
sleep 10
/usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
-f /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
--jobid $1 --username $2 &> /root/prologue.txt
# chmod 500 /var/torque/mom_priv/prologue
```

- on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/mom_priv/prologue
#!/bin/bash

while [ ! -f /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec ];
do sleep 3 ;
done
sleep 10
/usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
-f /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
--jobid $1 --username $2 &> /root/prologue.txt
# chmod 500 /var/lib/torque/mom_priv/prologue
```

19. Configure the wnodes_nameserver service

```
# cp /etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.template
```

```
/etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.ini
# cat /etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.ini
[<VLAN>]
network_type = OPEN
bait_host =
vm_host = test-1.<domain>^<MAC 1>;test-2.<domain>^<MAC 2>
# cat /etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_bait_config.ini
[BAIT_CONF]
...
HOST_GROUP_<valuebait>=test*
ENABLED_VLAN_GROUP_<valuebait>=<VLAN name>
USE_LVM=NO
BATCH_SYSTEM_TYPE = PBS
ENABLE_MIXED_MODE = yes
type = BATCH_REAL
PX_FAILED_RETURN_STATUS = 3
# cat /etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_hv_config.ini
[HV_CONF]
...
USE_LVM=NO
HOST_GROUP_<valuehv>=test*
ENABLED_VLAN_GROUP_<valuehv>=<VLAN name>
ENABLE_MIXED_MODE=yes
```

20. Start the wnodes_nameserver service

```
# service wnodes_nameserver start
```

21. Configure the wnodes_manager cli

```
# cat /etc/wnodes/manager/wnodes.ini
...
NS_HOST = <hostname namserver>.<domain>
...
```

22. Add image

```
# wnodes_manager -a wnodes-emi-images http
torquemada.cr.cnaf.infn.it/wnodes/wnodes_sl5_wn_tf
x86_64 raw /dev/mapper/VolGroup00-LogVol100
```

23. Verify the registration of the image

```
# wnodes_manager -l
```

24. Configure the `wnodes_hypervisor` server

```
# cat /etc/wnodes/hypervisor/wnodes.ini
...
NS_HOST = <hostname namserver>.<domain>
...
```

25. Configure the `wnodes_bait` server

```
# cat /etc/wnodes/bait/wnodes.ini
...
NS_HOST = <hostname namserver>.<domain>
...
```

26. Start the `wnodes_hypervisor` server

```
# service wnodes_hypervisor start
```

27. Verify the `wnodes_bait` server

```
# service wnodes_bait status
```

3.1.3 WORKER NODE ON A GIVEN IMAGE

1. Get an image with one of the supported Operating System: SL5 64 bit, SL6 64 bit

2. Disable `iptables` service:

```
# iptables -F
# chkconfig iptables off
# service iptables stop
```

3. Disable `selinux`

4. Not require host certificate

5. Satisfy common repository settings:

- on `sl5`

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/5/x86_64/
epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm
```

- on `sl6`

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/6/x86_64/  
epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm
```

6. Satisfy EMI repository settings:

- on sl5

```
# wget http://emisoft.web.cern.ch/emisoft/dist/EMI/3/sl5/x86_64/  
base/emi-release-3.0.0-1.el5.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck emi-release-3.0.0-1.el5.noarch.rpm
```

- on sl6

```
# wget http://emisoft.web.cern.ch/emisoft/dist/EMI/3/sl6/x86_64/  
base/emi-release-3.0.0-1.el6.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck emi-release-3.0.0-1.el6.noarch.rpm
```

7. Satisfy EGI repository settings to install EMI Worker Node

```
# wget http://repository.egi.eu/software/production/cas/1/current/  
repo-files/EGI-trustanchors.repo -O /etc/yum.repos.d/EGI-trustanchors.repo
```

8. Clean YUM cache

```
# yum clean all  
# yum makecache
```

9. Install Torque/Maui client

- with EMI configuration

```
# yum install ca-policy-egi-core  
# yum install lcg-CA  
# yum install emi-wn emi-torque-client
```

- without EMI configuration

```
# yum install torque-client torque-mom
```

10. Install WNoDeS

```
# yum install wnodes_site_specific
```

11. Configure the Torque/Maui client

- on the client host

- with EMI configuration

- (a) Edit def file

```
# cat site-info.def
CE_HOST=emi-demo13.$MY_DOMAIN
CE_SMP_SIZE=2
BATCH_SERVER=$CE_HOST
```

```
JOB_MANAGER=pbs
CE_BATCH_SYS=pbs
BATCH_BIN_DIR=/usr/bin
BATCH_VERSION=torque-<version>
BATCH_LOG_DIR=/var/torque
BATCH_CONF_DIR=/opt/
```

- (b) Run yaim

```
# /opt/glite/yaim/bin/yaim -v -c -s site-info.def
-n WN -n TORQUE_client
```

- (c) get the munge.key file from the Torque server host and copy in /etc/munge/

- (d) verify munge key

```
# chown munge /etc/munge/munge.key
# ll /etc/munge/munge.key
-r----- 1 munge root 1024 Mar 15 17:47 /etc/munge/munge.key
```

- (e) Enable munge service

```
# chkconfig munge on
# service munge start
```

- without EMI configuration

- (a) Create node file

- * on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/mom_priv/config
$pbsserver <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$restricted <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$logevent 255
$ideal_load 2.5
$max_load 2.4
```

- * on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/mom_priv/config
$pbsserver <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$restricted <hostname pbs server>.<domain>
$logevent 255
$ideal_load 2.5
$max_load 2.4
```

(b) Enable pbs_mom service

```
# chkconfig pbs_mom on
# service pbs_mom restart
```

(c) Get the munge.key file from the Torque server host and copy in /etc/munge/

(d) Verify munge key

```
# chown munge /etc/munge/munge.key
# ll /etc/munge/munge.key
-r----- 1 munge root 1024 Mar 15 17:47 /etc/munge/munge.key
```

(e) Enable munge service

```
# chkconfig munge on
# service munge start
```

(f) Set torque server hostname

* on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/server_config
<hostname torque>.<domain>
```

* on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/server_config
<hostname torque>.<domain>
```

12. Enable ssh without password

```
# cat /etc/ssh/ssh_config
...
PasswordAuthentication yes
EnableSSHKeySign yes
HostbasedAuthentication yes
StrictHostKeyChecking no
```

13. Configure the wnodes_preexec service

```
# chmod 500 /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
# cp /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf.tpl
  /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf
# cat /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf
[general]
TMPFILE=/tmp/my_bait
LOCAL_DOMAIN =cnaf.infn.it
NS_HOST=<hostname nameserver>.<domain>
NS_PORT=8219
BAIT_PORT=8111
FAIL_RETURN_STATUS=3
```

```
[default]
TYPE=BATCH
IMG=wnodes_tf_wn
NETWORK_TYPE=OPEN
CPU=1
MEM=2500
STORAGE=30
ENABLEVIRTIO=YES
BANDWIDTH=10
PX_SCRIPT=
```

- on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/mom_priv/prologue
#!/bin/bash

while [ ! -f /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec ];
do sleep 3 ;
done
sleep 10
/usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
-f /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf
--jobid $1 --username $2 &> /root/prologue.txt
#
# chmod 500 /var/torque/mom_priv/prologue
```

- on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/mom_priv/prologue
#!/bin/bash

while [ ! -f /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec ];
do sleep 3 ;
done
sleep 10
/usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
-f /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf
--jobid $1 --username $2 &> /root/prologue.txt
#
# chmod 500 /var/lib/torque/mom_priv/prologue
```

3.2 WNODES OCCI SERVER

1. Install one of the supported Operating System: SL5 64 bit, SL6 64 bit

2. Import the GPG key for EMI packages:

```
# rpm --import http://emisoft.web.cern.ch/emisoft/dist/EMI/3/RPM-GPG-KEY-emi
```

3. Satisfy common repository settings:

- on sl5

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/5/x86_64/  
epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm
```

- on sl6

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/6/x86_64/  
epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm
```

4. Satisfy EMI repository settings:

- on sl5

```
# wget -O /etc/yum.repos.d/emi-3-rc-sl5.repo  
http://eticssoft.web.cern.ch/eticssoft/mock/emi-3-rc-sl5.repo
```

- on sl6

```
# wget -O /etc/yum.repos.d/emi-3-rc-sl6.repo  
http://eticssoft.web.cern.ch/eticssoft/mock/emi-3-rc-sl6.repo
```

5. Satisfy EGI repository settings to install EMI Worker Node

```
# wget http://repository.egi.eu/software/production/cas/1/current/  
repo-files/EGI-trustanchors.repo -O /etc/yum.repos.d/EGI-trustanchors.repo
```

6. Clean YUM cache

```
# yum clean all  
# yum makecache
```

7. Install the ca-policy-egi-core package

```
# yum install ca-policy-egi-core
```

8. Install the fetch-crl package

```
# yum install fetch-crl
```

9. Install the xml-commons-apis package

```
# yum install xml-commons-apis
```

10. Activate the fetch-crl cron service for checking CRLs periodically

```
# service fetch-crl-cron start
```

11. Run the fetch-crl command

```
# /usr/sbin/fetch-crl &
```

12. Install the wnodes_cloud package

```
# yum install wnodes_cloud
```

13. In order to setup Tomcat for working with CaNL, edit the tomcat configuration file <TOMCAT_DIR>/conf/server.xml. An example is reported below:

```
<Connector port="8080" protocol="HTTP/1.1"
  connectionTimeout="20000"
  redirectPort="8443" />

<Connector port="8443" SSLEnabled="true"
  maxThreads="150" minSpareThreads="25" maxSpareThreads="75"
  enableLookups="false" disableUploadTimeout="true"
  acceptCount="100" debug="0" scheme="https" secure="true"
  sslImplementation="eu.emi.security.canl.tomcat.CANLSSLImplementation"
  truststore="/etc/grid-security/certificates"
  hostcert="/etc/grid-security/tomcat-cert.pem"
  hostkey="/etc/grid-security/tomcat-key.pem"
  updateInterval="3600000"
  clientAuth="true" sslProtocol="TLS"
  crlcheckingmode="require"/>
```

Note: to make tomcat5 work properly after a fresh install, check the following link:

<https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/EMI/CANLTomcatPlugin>

14. Start the wnodes_cloud service:

- on sl5

```
# service tomcat5 restart
```

- on sl6

```
# service tomcat6 restart
```

3.3 WNODES CACHEMANAGER SERVICE

1. Install one of the supported Operating System: SL5 64 bit, SL6 64 bit

2. Disable iptables service:

```
# iptables -F  
# chkconfig iptables off  
# service iptables stop
```

3. Disable selinux

4. Not require host certificate

5. Satisfy common repository settings:

- on sl5

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/5/x86_64/  
epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-5-4.noarch.rpm
```

- on sl6

```
# wget http://archives.fedoraproject.org/pub/epel/6/x86_64/  
epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck epel-release-6-7.noarch.rpm
```

6. Satisfy EMI repository settings:

- on sl5

```
# wget http://emisoft.web.cern.ch/emisoft/dist/EMI/3/sl5/x86_64/  
base/emi-release-3.0.0-1.el5.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck emi-release-3.0.0-1.el5.noarch.rpm
```

- on sl6

```
# wget http://emisoft.web.cern.ch/emisoft/dist/EMI/3/sl6/x86_64/  
base/emi-release-3.0.0-1.el6.noarch.rpm  
# yum localinstall --nogpgcheck emi-release-3.0.0-1.el6.noarch.rpm
```

7. Satisfy EGI repository settings to install EMI Worker Node

```
# wget http://repository.egi.eu/software/production/cas/1/current/  
repo-files/EGI-trustanchors.repo -O /etc/yum.repos.d/EGI-trustanchors.repo
```

8. Clean YUM cache

```
# yum clean all  
# yum makecache
```

9. Install Torque/Maui client

- with EMI configuration

```
# yum install ca-policy-egi-core  
# yum install lcg-CA  
# yum install emi-wn emi-torque-client
```

- without EMI configuration

```
# yum install torque-client torque-mom
```

10. Install WNoDeS cachemanager

```
# yum install wnodes_cachemanager
```

11. Configure the Torque/Maui client

- on the client host
 - with EMI configuration

(a) Edit def file

```
# cat site-info.def  
CE_HOST=emi-demo13.$MY_DOMAIN  
CE_SMP_SIZE=2  
BATCH_SERVER=$CE_HOST  
  
JOB_MANAGER=pbs  
CE_BATCH_SYS=pbs  
BATCH_BIN_DIR=/usr/bin  
BATCH_VERSION=torque-<version>  
BATCH_LOG_DIR=/var/torque  
BATCH_CONF_DIR=/opt/
```

(b) Run yaim

```
# /opt/glite/yaim/bin/yaim -v -c -s site-info.def  
-n WN -n TORQUE_client
```

(c) Verify munge key

```
# chown munge /etc/munge/munge.key  
# ll /etc/munge/munge.key  
-r----- 1 munge root 1024 Mar 15 17:47 /etc/munge/munge.key
```

(d) Enable munge service

```
# chkconfig munge on  
# service munge start
```

– without EMI configuration

(a) Create node file

* on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/mom_priv/config  
$pbsserver <hostname pbs server>.<domain>  
$restricted <hostname pbs server>.<domain>  
$logevent 255  
$ideal_load 2.5  
$max_load 2.4
```

* on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/mom_priv/config  
$pbsserver <hostname pbs server>.<domain>  
$restricted <hostname pbs server>.<domain>  
$logevent 255  
$ideal_load 2.5  
$max_load 2.4
```

(b) Enable pbs_mom service

```
# chkconfig pbs_mom on  
# service pbs_mom restart
```

(c) Get the munge.key file from the Torque server host and copy it in /etc/munge/

(d) Verify munge key

```
# chown munge /etc/munge/munge.key  
# ll /etc/munge/munge.key  
-r----- 1 munge root 1024 Mar 15 17:47 /etc/munge/munge.key
```

(e) Enable munge server

```
# chkconfig munge on  
# service munge start
```

(f) Set torque hostname server

* on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/server_name  
<hostname torque>.<domain>
```

* on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/server_name  
<hostname torque>.<domain>
```

• on the server host

(a) Add the new host that contains the `wnodes_cachemanager` service to the nodes file

– on sl5

```
# cat /var/torque/server_priv/nodes  
<hostname>.<domain> np=4 wnodes bait  
...
```

– on sl6

```
# cat /var/lib/torque/server_priv/nodes  
<hostname>.<domain> np=4 wnodes bait  
...
```

(b) Restart `pbs_server` server

```
# service pbs_server start
```

(c) Add the new host that contains the `wnodes_bait` service to the maui file

```
# cat /var/spool/maui/maui.cfg  
...  
CLASSCFG[wnodes]          PLIST=virtual PDEF=virtual  
NODECFG[<hostname>.<domain>] PARITION=virtual
```

(d) Restart `maui` server

```
# service maui start
```

12. Enable ssh without password

```
# cat /etc/ssh/ssh_config  
...  
PasswordAuthentication yes  
EnableSSHKeysign yes  
HostbasedAuthentication yes  
StrictHostKeyChecking no
```

13. Set the `wnodes_cachemanager` database

(a) start `mysqld`

```
# service mysqld start
```

(b) create `wnodes_cachemanager` database the name of which is `<database name>`

```
# mysql -u root
#mysql> create database <database name>;
```

(c) set a password to the created `wnodes_cachemanager` database

```
# mysqladmin -u root password <password value>
```

(d) enter in the database with the set password and grant OCCl server host

```
# mysql -u root -p<password value> <database name>
# mysql> grant all privileges on <database name>.* to
'root'@'<OCCI server host IP>' identified by '<password value>' with grant option;
# mysql> flush privileges;
```

14. create client key without pw

```
# ssh-keygen
```

15. verify host certificate and CA

```
# ll /etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem
# ll /etc/grid-security/hostkey.pem
# ll /etc/grid-security/certificates/<CA>.pem
```

16. cat `/etc/wnodes/cachemanager/`

```
[CM_CONF]
CACHE_SIZE = 3
# time to wait between the cache refreshing (seconds)
CACHE_REFRESH_INTERVAL = 60.0
DATABASE = mysql://root:<password value>@localhost/<database name>
MAX_LOG_SIZE =
LOGFILE =
TIMEOUT = 30.0
PORT = 54321
# HOSTNAME = <cachemanager fully qualified hostname>
```

```
[BATCH_SYS]
TYPE = <type of batch system>
USER = cloud
QUEUE = <batch queue>
```

```
[BAIT_CONF]
PORT = 8111
```

```
[NS_CONF]
HOST = <nameserver fully qualified hostname>
PORT = 8219

[WEBAPP_CONF]
HOST = localhost

[DEFAULT_VM_OPTION]
CPU = 1
BANDWIDTH = 10
IMG = <image name>
MEM = 1700
MOUNT = t3-cnfs.cr.cnaf.infn.it:/gpfs_home/home/CMS-T3:/home/CMS-T3
STORAGE = 50

[KEY_CERT]
CA_CERT = /etc/grid-security/certificates/INFN-CA-2006.pem
CM_PRIVATE_KEY = /root/.ssh/id_rsa
CM_PUBLIC_KEY = /root/.ssh/id_rsa.pub
SERVER_CERT = /etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem
SERVER_KEY = /etc/grid-security/hostkey.pem
```

17. Start the wnodes_cachemanager service

```
# service wnodes_cachemanager start
```

4 INSTALLATION PREREQUISITES

4.1 OPERATING SYSTEM

All WNoDeS components are certified to work on Scientific Linux SL5 x86_64 and SL6 x86_64 with EPEL as repository for external dependencies.

4.2 DNS

Full access to the DNS configuration is needed in order to add each virtual machine hostname, which is used to instantiate a virtual resource. Host resolution will be used by DHCP to provide ip address to the virtual resource.

The hostname for the `wnodes_bait` service should contain 'bait' in case of Mixed Mode disabled.

4.3 DHCP

Full access to the DHCP configuration is needed in order to configure the mapping from mac address to hostname for each hostname that is used to instantiate virtual machine.

4.4 KVM

KVM needs to be installed on all the nodes where the hypervisor service runs.

4.5 REPOSITORY DISTRIBUTION

A dedicated repository for the virtual machine images needs to be configured. It could be a Web Server or a shared file system such as the common NFS, Lustre and GPFS. In the former, a http repository needs to be configured.

4.6 IMAGE

Use `virtio` driver to define the image.

4.7 BATCH SYSTEM

The batch system either LSF or Torque/Maui needs to be installed and configured.

In case of PBS, the Computing Elements, worker nodes and submission nodes are configured to allow `ssh` connection without requiring password: each worker node could login without password to the Computing Element and among worker nodes. It is suggested to put the same `ssh` host keys in all the nodes (i.e., both bait and worker node) in order to easy the managing of the host list.

4.8 CERTIFICATES

The host where the OCCI service and the `wnodes_cachemanager` service run must have a valid certificate installed, usually located in `/etc/grid-security`.

4.8.1 OCCI SERVER

In order to allow tomcat to access these credentials, duplicate hostcert and hostkey files and assign the ownership to the tomcat user:

```
cp -a /etc/grid-security/hostkey.pem /etc/grid-security/tomcat-key.pem
cp -a /etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem /etc/grid-security/tomcat-cert.pem
chown tomcat.root /etc/grid-security/tomcat-*
```

4.9 PUB KEY

The pub key used by the `wnodes_hypervisor` services is also used by the `wnodes_cachemanager` service.

5 WNODES INSTALLATION RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 WNODES_NAMESERVER

The `wnodes_nameserver` service can be installed on any machine that is not used as hypervisor. It can be both virtual or physical. **This service contains the configurations of hypervisor and bait.**

Please use the following package:

```
wnodes_nameserver
```

Log files are produced under `/var/log/wnodes/nameserver`. Standard error and standard output files are produced under `/tmp`.

5.2 WNODES_MANAGER

The `wnodes_manager` CLI can be installed on any machine or laptop.

Please use the following package:

```
wnodes_manager
```

5.3 WNODES_HYPERVERISOR

The `wnodes_hypervisor` service can be installed on any machine, where the virtualization technology is enabled. As detailed in Section 3, the behaviour of the `wnodes_hypervisor` service depend on the mixed mode feature:

- If the feature is not enabled, then the `wnodes_hypervisor` service will instantiate a virtual machine that contains the `wnodes_bait` service. Therefore, the image of that virtual machine needs to be created with the bait software and added to the WNoDeS repository before starting the `wnodes_hypervisor` service.
- If the feature is enabled, the `wnodes_hypervisor` service will be able to execute jobs.

Please use the following package:

```
wnodes_hypervisor
```

Log files are produced under `/var/log/wnodes/hypervisor`. Standard error and standard output files are produced under `/tmp`.

5.4 WNODES_BAIT

As detailed in Section 3, the installation and configuration of the `wnodes_bait` service depend on the mixed mode feature:

- If the feature is not enabled, then the `wnodes_bait` service will run on a virtual machine that is automatically instantiated by the `wnodes_hypervisor` service.
- If the feature is enabled, the `wnodes_bait` service will run on the same machine where the `wnodes_hypervisor` service runs.

Please use the following package:

`wnodes_bait`

Log files are produced under `/var/log/wnodes/bait`. Standard error and standard output files are produced under `/tmp`.

5.5 WNODES_SITE_SPECIFIC

The `wnodes_site_specific` component contains, among other things, the `wnodes_preexec` script that sends a request to the `wnodes_bait` service in order to instantiate a virtual machine that can be used to execute a job.

The `wnodes_preexec` script and its configuration file need to be present on the machines where jobs are executed. In case of a shared FS, the `wnodes_preexec` script and its configuration file can be copied in a common area: otherwise, you need to install them in all the machines specifying the same configuration file.

Please use the following package:

`wnodes_site_specific`

Debug Log file is produced under `/tmp` with the name `<user>_debug_px_wnodes`, where `<user>` is who has submitted the job.

5.6 WNODES OCCI SERVER

- Since the authentication process is based on the classic `gridmapfile` mechanism, it is required to check this file is periodically generated by the `edg-mkgridmap` command. The `gridmapfile` location must be provided in the `gridmapfile location` section of the `application.properties` configuration file. See Section for further details.
- Before starting the service be sure the server ip is allowed to access the WNoDeS Cache Manager database.

6 NAMESERVER CONFIGURATION

The `wnodes_nameserver` configuration files that need to be edited are:

- mac list file
- wnodes hypervisor file
- wnodes bait file

6.1 WNODES NAMESERVER MAC LIST FILE

The `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.ini` file has an INI format in which each section corresponds to a given VLAN and the content of each section shows details of the specified VLAN. The file contains the following information:

```
[<VLAN_NAME>]
network_type = OPEN
bait_host = <fully bait hostname>^00:16:3e:01:00:16;...
vm_host = <fully virtual image hostname>^00:16:3e:01:00:16;...
```

where `<VLAN_NAME>` is the section that expresses the name of the VLAN, whose value can be a set of integer numbers or the `DEFAULT_VLAN` string, which is chosen when the virtual image hostnames belong to the same VLAN of the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname. The section contains the following options:

network_type can have the `OPEN` value or the `CLOSE` value (see Table 2);

bait_host is a list of values separated by `;` whose value expresses hostname and mac address linked by the `^` symbol. **If the mixed mode feature is enabled, bait_host can be empty;**

vm_host is a list of values separated by `;` whose value expresses hostname and mac address linked by the `^` symbol.

All the hostnames must be defined in the DNS, while the mac addresses with the related IP addresses in the DHCP.

Table 2: The description of network type values

Network Type Value	Description
OPEN	It means that the related VLAN is able to access to the local network.
CLOSE	It means that the related VLAN is able to access to the external network and disable to access to the local sub networks. It is defined for the network isolation of the virtual machine in order to open to the network of virtual machine externally but not internally. Typically virtual machine that is used to run jobs has the <code>network_type</code> value set to <code>OPEN</code> .

6.2 WNODES HYPERVISOR FILE

The `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_hv_config.ini` file has an INI format. The file contains the following information:

```
[HV_CONF]
HV_PORT=8222
BAIT_PORT=8111

LOG_FILE_NAME=wnodes_hv.log

MAX_LOG_FILE_SIZE=100000
MAX_COUNT_LOG_FILE=5

LOCAL_REPO_DIR=/etc/wnodes/repo

BAIT_IMG_TAG=<image tag>
BAIT_VM_RAM=800

HOST_GROUP_<ALL>=
ENABLED_VLAN_GROUP_<ALL>=DEFAULT_VLAN

SSH_KEY_FILE=/etc/wnodes/hypervisor/.ssh/hv_id_rsa

USE_LVM=YES
VOLUME_GROUP=vg0

SERVICE_NIC_IP=<IP NIC Service>
SERVICE_NIC_IP_MASK=<MASK IP NIC Service>

DNS_RANGE=<DNS RANGE 1,DNS RANGE 2>
DNS_LEASE_TIME=5m
```

where `HV_CONF` is the name of the section that contains the following options:

HV_PORT specifies the port of the `wnodes_hypervisor` service;

BAIT_PORT specifies the port of the `wnodes_bait` service;

LOG_FILE_NAME specifies the logging file name;

MAX_LOG_FILE_SIZE specifies the maximum size of the logging file name. The size is expressed in Byte;

MAX_COUNT_LOG_FILE specifies the maximum number of rotations of the logging file name. The value 5 means that after 5 rotations the first is removed;

LOCAL_REPO_DIR specifies the repository directory of images that the `wnodes_hypervisor` service download;

BAIT_IMG_TAG specifies the tag name of the virtual machine associated to the bait. The `wnodes_hypervisor` service will get the image of the virtual machine related to the tag. **The value of this option is only considered with mixed mode disabled;**

BAIT_VM_RAM specified the amount of RAM to allocate in the virtual machine where the `wnodes_bait` service will run. **The value of this option is only considered with mixed mode disabled.**

The following two options need to be specified in pair:

HOST_GROUP_<ALL> specifies a set of regular expressions separated by `;`. It represents groups of hostnames that belong to given VLANs with `<ALL>` as its logical name;

ENABLED_VLAN_GROUP_<ALL> specifies the enabled VLANs for the logical name that are associated to groups of hostnames. Please use `DEFAULT_VLAN` to refer to the VLAN of the `wnodes_hypervisor` service;

SSH_KEY_FILE is the location of the rsa key that is created by the `wnodes_hypervisor` service during its start and saved there;

USE_LVM is a flag whose value can be yes or no. If it is yes, this means that the `wnodes_hypervisor` service will define and create a file system to be associated to the virtual machine that will be instantiated. LVM stands for logical volume;

VOLUME_GROUP specifies the name of the volume group to be set before creating the logical volume;

SERVICE_NIC_IP specifies the physical address of the `wnodes_hypervisor` interface used to interact with the virtual machine;

SERVICE_NIC_IP_MASK specifies the mask address of the `wnodes_hypervisor` interface used to interact with the virtual machine;

DNS_RANGE specifies the range of the addresses that the DHCP server can assign to the virtual machine. This option starts with `DNS` because the service used to change the DHCP is called `dnsmasq`;

DNS_LEASE_TIME specifies the time in which the address is not used. After that the address is used for another virtual machine.

6.3 WNODES BAIT FILE

The `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_bait_config.ini` file has an INI format. The file contains the following information:

```
[BAIT_CONF]
BATCH_SYSTEM_TYPE=<Type of the batch system>

HV_PORT=8222
BAIT_PORT=8111

LOG_FILE_NAME=wnodes_bait.log

MAX_LOG_FILE_SIZE=100000
```

```
MAX_COUNT_LOG_FILE=5
```

```
HOST_GROUP_<ALL>=  
ENABLED_VLAN_GROUP_<ALL>=DEFAULT_VLAN
```

```
VM_UNREACH_TIMEOUT=200
```

```
STATUS_RETRY_COUNT=3  
SCHEDULING_INTERVAL=60  
RESERVATION_LENGTH=1200  
USE_LVM=YES
```

```
TYPE=<Types of request>
```

```
PX_FAILED_RETURN_STATUS=1
```

```
DEFAULT_VM_IMG=  
DEFAULT_VM_MEM=2000  
DEFAULT_VM_CPU=1  
DEFAULT_VM_BANDWIDTH=50  
DEFAULT_VM_STORAGE=10  
DEFAULT_JOB_TYPE=<Type of request>
```

```
MAX_VM_MEM=3000  
MAX_VM_BANDWIDTH=100  
MAX_VM_CPU=8  
MAX_VM_STORAGE=100  
MIN_VM_MEM=1500  
MIN_VM_BANDWIDTH=10  
MIN_VM_CPU=1  
MIN_VM_STORAGE=10
```

```
MIXED_MODE=yes
```

where `BAIT_CONF` is the name of the section that contains the following options:

BATCH_SYSTEM_TYPE specifies the type of batch system. If it is set to `LSF`, the batch system will be `LSF`. If it is set to `PBS`, the batch system will be `Torque/Maui`;

HV_PORT specifies the port number of the `wnodes_hypervisor` service;

BAIT_PORT specifies the port number of the `wnodes_bait` service;

LOG_FILE_NAME specifies the logging filename;

MAX_LOG_FILE_SIZE specifies the maximum size of the logging filename;

MAX_COUNT_LOG_FILE specifies the maximum number of rotations of the logging file name. The value 5 means that after 5 rotations the first is removed;

The following two options need to be specified in pair:

HOST_GROUP_<ALL> specifies a set of regular expressions separated by ; . It represents groups of hostnames that belong to given VLANs with <ALL> as its logical name;

ENABLED_VLAN_GROUP_<ALL> specifies the enabled VLANs for the logical name that are associated to groups of hostnames. Please use `DEFAULT_VLAN` to refer to the VLAN of the `wnodes_hypervisor` service;

VM_UNREACH_TIMEOUT represents the default timeout in seconds that is used when the instantiated virtual machine is unreachable (e.g., the instantiate virtual machine can be unreachable because the DHCP service has not provided the correct address.). After having reached the specified timeout, the virtual machine is destroyed and then created again;

STATUS_RETRY_COUNT is the number of times a virtual machine can stay on the same status. After that the request is rejected;

SCHEDULING_INTERVAL is the interval of the batch system to schedule new jobs;

RESERVATION_LENGTH is used when the batch system is LSF. It represents the length of the reservation;

USE_LVM specifies if the `wnodes_hypervisor` service creates the LVM for each virtual machine. If it is set to NO, then the `wnodes_bait` service will not consider the storage resource. The mandatory resources are: CPU, RAM, network and storage;

TYPE is a list of types of requests that the `wnodes_bait` service can accept to create virtual machines. The possible types are `BATCH`, and `BATCH_REAL` separated by ; . If it contains `BATCH`, then the bait service will accept batch jobs. If it contains `BATCH_REAL`, then the bait service will accept real jobs;

PX_FAILED_RETURN_STATUS represents the return status of the `preexec` service in order to send the job, which the virtual machine has been created for, in the queue of the batch system. In case of LSF the value is greater than 0, while for PBS the value is greater than 2;

The following default values represent the default values of the virtual machine parameters when they are not specified in the request:

DEFAULT_VM_IMG is the default value of the virtual machine image;

DEFAULT_VM_MEM is the default value of the virtual machine memory;

DEFAULT_VM_CPU is the default value of the virtual machine cpu;

DEFAULT_VM_BANDWIDTH is the default value of the virtual machine bandwidth;

DEFAULT_VM_STORAGE is the default value of the virtual machine storage;

DEFAULT_JOB_TYPE is the default value of the virtual machine image;

The following maximum values represent the values that can be specified in a request:

MAX_VM_MEM is the maximum value of the virtual machine memory;

MAX_VM_BANDWIDTH is the maximum value of the virtual machine bandwidth;

MAX_VM_CPU is the maximum value of the virtual machine cpu;

MAX_VM_STORAGE is the maximum value of the virtual machine storage;

The following minimum values represent the values below which the bait service cannot accept requests to instantiate virtual machines, that is the set batch system does not consider this particular bait able to accept new jobs:

MIN_VM_MEM is the minimum value of the virtual machine memory;

MIN_VM_BANDWIDTH is the minimum value of the virtual machine bandwidth;

MIN_VM_CPU is the minimum value of the virtual machine cpu;

MIN_VM_STORAGE is the minimum value of the virtual machine storage;

MIXED_MODE specifies if the mixed mode feature is enabled.

6.4 WNODES NAMESERVER STATE

`(/var/log/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_ns_state)`

7 MANAGER CONFIGURATION

The `wnodes_manager` configuration file that needs to be edited is `/etc/wnodes/manager/wnodes.ini`. It has an INI format and contains the following information:

```
[NAMESERVER]
NS_HOST=<myhost>.<mydomain>
NS_PORT=8219
```

where `NAMESERVER` is the name of the section that contains the following options:

NS_HOST is the fully qualified hostname where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs;

NS_PORT is the port number where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs.

7.1 OPTIONS TO HANDLE VIRTUAL MACHINE IMAGES

The `Manager` CLI is responsible for the configuration of the repository of the virtual machine images. The repository is composed of files.

This CLI associates a tag to each virtual machine image file: however, more tags can be linked to the same virtual machine image file. The WNoDeS core services use this tag when they need to refer to a given virtual machine image file. The tag represents the unique identifier of the virtual machine image.

A tag is defined by the following parameters:

tag is a string that specifies the tag. Please use the following convention to specify the tag:

```
<name>_<os>_<arch>
```

where `name` is the name of the virtual machine image file, `os` is the operating system included in the virtual image file, `arch` is the architecture of the operating system.

location can take the `http` or `file` value. Please use `file` for local filesystem or filesystem mounted locally (e.g., `gpfs`), while use `http` for web repository.

path is a string that specifies the address of the virtual machine image file.

arch can take several values such as `i386`, `i686`, and `x86_64`. It specifies the architecture of the virtual machine image file.

type can take several values such as `raw`, `qcow2`, `bochs`, `cloop`, `cow`, `dmg`, `iso`, `qcow`, `vmdk`, and `vpc`. It specifies the format of the virtual machine image file.

dev is the root file system of the image that will be used by the `libguestfs` package.

Please provide at least one image to the WNoDeS system. In this case the WNoDeS system will take care of tag's changes (and caching) automatically.

This CLI handles the following options in relation to the image:

- a/--add_image tag location path arch type** : the option, followed by an ordered-parameters list separated by a space, adds information about the virtual machine image file.
- purge_image_list** removes all the images information from the repository. **Please be careful.**
- d/--delete_image tag** : the option, followed by the `tag` parameter, deletes the tag and all the other information associated to the tag.
- g/--get_image_info tag** : the option, followed by the `tag` parameter, gets information about the virtual machine image file identified by the specified tag.
- l/--list_image** lists information about the registered virtual machine image files.
- r/--replace_image tag location path arch type** : the option, followed by an ordered-parameters list separated by a space, replaces information about the virtual machine image file.

7.2 OPTIONS TO OBTAIN VLANS INFORMATION

This CLI provides system administrators with options to retrieve information about VLANs that are specified in the `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.ini` file. Below these options are detailed:

- V/--list_vlan** provides a list of the VLANs registered in the current configuration.
- B/--list_baitname vlan** : the options, followed by the `vlan` name, provides a list of the bait hostnames registered in a specific VLAN configuration. For example, `BAITNAME=vwn-0001-bait.infn.it`
`MAC= 00:16:3e:00:00:01`
- L/--list_hostname vlan** : the options, followed by the `vlan` name, provides a list of the virtual machine hostnames registered in a specific VLAN configuration. For example, `HOSTNAME=vwn-0001.infn.it`
`MAC= 00:16:3e:00:00:01`
- N/--list_network_type vlan** : the options, followed by the `vlan` name, provides information about the network type (e.g., open/closed) of a specific VLAN.
- O/--list_option_values option vlan** : the option, followed by an ordered-parameters list separated by a space, provides information about the values of the given option for the specified VLAN. This option is useful to handle new options in the `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.ini` file that do not have a specific method in the code.

7.3 OPTIONS TO MODIFY THE REGISTERED HOSTNAMES

The following options change the `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.ini` file in order to modify the registered hostnames:

- A/--add_hostname hostname vlan** : the option, followed by a virtual machine hostname with the mac address and a `vlan` name, adds the virtual machine hostname to the specific `vlan`.
- T/--add_baitname baitname vlan** : the option, followed by a bait hostname with the mac address and a `vlan` name, adds the bait hostname to the specific `vlan`.
- D/--delete_hostname hostname vlan** : the option, followed by a virtual machine hostname with the mac address and a `vlan` name, deletes the virtual machine hostname from the specific `vlan`.

-E/--delete_baitname *baitname* *vlan* : the option, followed by a bait hostname with the mac address and a vlan name, deletes the bait hostname from the specific vlan.

In order to actuate the following options, the `wnodes_nameserver` must be stopped after any change and its status file (`/var/log/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_ns_state`) must be deleted. **Warning:** as consequence the status of the deployed bait hostnames and virtual machine hostnames will be lost. For this reason, it is highly recommended to stop all the hypervisor services before restarting the `wnodes_nameserver` service.

7.4 OPTIONS TO MANAGE THE CONFIGURATION FILES OF THE `WNODES_BAIT` AND `WNODES_HYPERSVISOR` SERVICES

WNoDeS provides centralized configuration files (that are identified with the `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_hv_config.ini` file and `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_bait_config.ini` file) for all the `wnodes_hypervisor` and `wnodes_bait` services. These files can be verified and modified by using the following options:

-v/--list_hv_config lists the values of the options specified in the `wnodes_hypervisor` configuration file.

-b/--list_bait_config lists the values of the options specified in the bait configuration file.

-P/--replace_hv_config *option value* : the option, followed by the option name and its value, replaces the value of the option in the `wnodes_hypervisor` configuration file.

-p/--replace_bait_config *option value* : the option, followed by the option name and its value, replaces the value of the option in the `wnodes_bait` configuration file.

The changes will affect all the new deployed `wnodes_hypervisor` and `wnodes_bait` services **and the old if rebooted TO BE CHECKED.**

Tip: in order to reload any change in a specific service configuration, the `reload_host_config` option can be used.

7.5 OPTIONS TO MANAGE THE `WNODES_BAIT` AND `WNODES_HYPERSVISOR` STATUS

The status of the `wnodes_bait` and `wnodes_hypervisor` services are handled by using the following options:

-o/--get_config *host port* : the option, followed by the hostname and port values, contacts the relative server and asks the current configuration.

-s/--get_bait_status *host* : the option, followed by the bait hostname value, gets the status for the specified bait. The value can also contain a regular expression.

-S/--get_hv_status *host* : the option, followed by the virtual machine hostname value, gets the status for the specified `wnodes_hypervisor`;

-R/--reload_host_config *host port* : the option, followed by the virtual machine hostname and port values, reloads the configuration of the specified service;

- t/-hv_connection host** : the option, followed by the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname value, gets the virtual machine connected to the specified `wnodes_hypervisor` service. The value can contain 'all': in this case the option will return all the deployed `wnodes_hypervisor` hostnames and their virtual machine hostnames;
- bait_connection host** : the option, followed by the bait hostname value, gets the virtual machine connected to the specified bait service. The value can also contain a regular expression;
- w/-open_bait host** : the option, followed by the bait hostname value, changes the status of the bait service in OPEN_ADMIN;
- x/-close_bait host (or 'all' or regular expression)** : the option, followed by the bait hostname value, changes the status of the bait in CLOSED_ADMIN. The value can contain 'all' or a regular expression;
- X/-destroy_VM_instance vm_hostname** : the option, followed by the virtual machine hostname value, destroys and removes the specified virtual machine instance;
- list_available_hostname** gets the available virtual machine hostnames (not yet assigned);
- list_available_baitname** gets the available bait hostnames (not yet assigned);
- list_active_hostname** get the active virtual machine hostnames;
- list_active_baitname** get the active bait hostnames;
- ping hostname port** : the option, followed by the hostname and port values of one of the WNoDeS services among `wnodes_hypervisor`, `wnodes_nameserver` and `wnodes_bait`, returns the version of the correspondent WNoDeS service.

8 HYPERVISOR CONFIGURATION

The `wnodes_hypervisor` configuration files that need to be edited are:

- `/etc/wnodes/hypervisor/wnodes.ini`
- `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_hv_config.ini` that is on the machine where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs. The information contained in the file is loaded by the `wnodes_hypervisor` service when it contacts the `wnodes_nameserver` service.

During its execution the `/var/log/wnodes/hypervisor/hv_network_current_status` file is created. It is on the same machine where the `wnodes_hypervisor` service runs. **WARNING: this file is internal to the `wnodes_hypervisor` service and cannot be removed.**

8.1 WNODES HYPERVISOR CONF

The `/etc/wnodes/hypervisor/wnodes.ini` file has an INI format and contains the following information:

```
[NAMESERVER]
NS_HOST=<fully nameserver hostname>
NS_PORT=8219
```

where `NAMESERVER` is the name of the section that contains the following options:

NS_HOST is the fully qualified hostname where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs;

NS_PORT is the port number where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs.

9 BAIT CONFIGURATION

The `wnodes_bait` configuration files that need to be edited are:

- `/etc/wnodes/bait/wnodes.ini`
- `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_bait_config.ini` that is on the machine where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs. The information contained in the file is loaded by the `wnodes_hypervisor` service when it contacts the `wnodes_nameserver` service.

9.1 WNODES BAIT CONF

The `/etc/wnodes/bait/wnodes.ini` file has an INI format and contains the following information:

```
[NAMESERVER]
NS_HOST=<fully nameserver hostname>
NS_PORT=8219
```

where `NAMESERVER` is the name of the section that contains the following options:

NS_HOST is the fully qualified hostname where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs;

NS_PORT is the port number where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs.

10 BATCH SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

10.1 LSF

The LSF configuration files that need to be edited are:

- cluster file
- batch site host file
- batch site queue file

Verify the setting of the `LSF_ENVDIR` environment variable.

10.1.1 LSF CLUSTER FILE

Add in the LSF cluster configuration file all the hostnames that WNoDeS will use to instantiate machines by editing the file `$(LSF_ENVDIR)/lsf.cluster.<cluster-name>` as follows:

```
HOSTNAME                model type server rlm mem swp RESOURCES
<virtual machine hostname> !      !    1      3.5 ()  ()  ()
```

where:

HOSTNAME specifies the name of the hostname;

model specifies CPU type;

type specifies the type of architecture. If it is set to `!`, then the architecture is determined by the batch system;

model `server` run job;

model `r1m` determines the load every minute;

model `RESOURCES` specified the resources specified on the machine.

Reconfigure lsf as follows:

```
$> lsadmin reconfig
```

Restart badmin as follows:

```
$> badmin mbdrestart
```

10.1.2 LSF BATCH SITE HOSTS FILE

Add in the LSF batch configuration file the same hostnames of above and define groups by editing the following file `$(LSF_ENVDIR)/lsbatch/<cluster-name>/configdir/lsb.hosts` as follows:

```
HOST_NAME           MXJ    r1m    pg     ls     tmp  DISPATCH_WINDOW  EXIT_RATE
<virtual machine hostname> 1      ()     ()     ()     ()   ()              ()
...
GROUP_NAME          GROUP_MEMBER
<group name>        (<virtual machine hostname 1> <virtual machine hostname 2> ...)
```

where:

HOST_NAME represents the name of the hostname;

MXJ represents the max number of jobs that can be run on the hostname. If it is equal to !, the batch system will calculate the number;

r1m

pg represents the page rate;

ls

tmp

DISPATCH_WINDOW tells that the hostname can be used in the dispatched window

EXIT_RATE represents the max number of failures within a dispatched window before the closure of the job;

GROUP_NAME

GROUP_MEMBER

Reconfigure lsf as follows:

```
$> lsadmin reconfig
```

Restart badmin as follows:

```
$> badmin mbdrestart
```

10.1.3 LSF BATCH SITE QUEUES FILE

Define or modify a queue to associate hostnames to the cluster by editing the file `$(LSF_ENVDIR)/lsbatch/<cluster-name>/configdir/lsb.queues` as follows:

```
Begin Queue
QUEUE_NAME    = wnodes_2_a
PRIORITY      = 10
JOB_ACCEPT_INTERVAL = 0
PRE_EXEC      = /usr/share/lsf/conf/scripts/wnodes_preexec
-f /usr/share/lsf/conf/wnodes_preexec
USERS         = all
HOSTS         = <virtual machine host 1> <virtual machine host 2> <machine host 1> ...
RES_REQ       = select[type==any]
DESCRIPTION   = Worker Node on Demand
End Queue
```

where

QUEUE_NAME represents the name of the queue.

PRIORITY is the batch system priority to decide which job can be run.

JOB_ACCEPT_INTERVAL defines the time interval in second between the execution of two jobs on the same host: if it is equal to 0, than jobs are executed at the same time; if it is equal to 100, than the time that elapses between the execution of two jobs is 100.

PRE_EXEC represents the location of the pre exec path file.

USERS represents the users that are enabled to use the queue.

HOSTS specifies the list of machines that are part of the queue.

RES_REQ selects machines: if it contains *type==any*, than it means that machines of any types (architectures) will be selected.

10.2 TORQUE/MAUI

The Torque/Maui (i.e., the batch manager/the batch scheduler respectively) configuration files that need to be edited are:

- nodes file for Torque
- maui file

10.2.1 NODES FILE

Add in the nodes configuration file the new nodes that WNoDeS will use to instantiate virtual machines and to run the `wnodes_bait` service by editing the file `nodes` as follows:

```
HOST_NAME      NP=SLOTS      PROPERTIES
<bait hostname>    np=2          wnodes bait
<virtual image hostname> np=1          <virtual image hostname>
```

HOSTNAME specifies the name of the hostname that will be added to the Torque server;

NP=SLOTS specifies the number of slots for the specific node;

PROPERTIES is a list of properties separated by an empty space. They are really important. In the above example, wnodes is the property of the queue where the WNoDeS jobs.

10.2.2 MAUI FILE

Configure maui in order to create a partition by editing the file `/var/spool/maui/maui.cfg`:

```
NODECFG[<bait hostname>] PARTITION=virtual
CLASSCFG[wnodes] PLIST=virtual PDEF=virtual
```

where `<bait hostname>` is the bait node that goes in a virtual partition, while `wnodes` is a queue that is included in the virtual class. This means that all the jobs that are on the same queue can be executed on the same partition.

10.2.3 CREATE A QUEUE

Create a dedicated queue called `<queue name>` for WNoDeS jobs by using the `qmgr` command as follows:

```
$> qmgr < queue_command
```

where `queue_command` is a file with the following content detailed in Table 3:

```
create queue <queue name>
set queue <queue name> queue_type = Execution
set queue <queue name> Priority = 1000000
set queue <queue name> max_running = 80
set queue <queue name> resources_max.cput = 100:00:00
set queue <queue name> resources_max.walltime = 100:00:00
set queue <queue name> resources_default.neednodes = wnodes
set queue <queue name> enabled = True
set queue <queue name> started = True
```

Table 3: The description of the properties used for the `<queue name>` queue

Property Name	Description
queue_type	It means that the queue could be used to execute jobs.
max_running	It specifies the max number of running jobs.
resources_max.cput	It specifies the limit on the CPU time usable by the jobs.
resources_max.walltime	It specifies the wall time limit for the job in this queue.
enabled	It means that the queue is enabled and could be used to submit jobs.
started	It specifies whether jobs in the queue are allowed to be executed.

10.2.4 MODIFY JOB MANAGEMENT

Configure the Torque server in order to allow job management from WNoDeS hosts (real machine and baits):

```
$> qmgr -c "set server managers += root@<fully bait hostname>"
$> qmgr -c "set server managers += root@<fully bait hostname>"
$> qmgr -c "set server managers += root@<fully bait hostname>"
$> qmgr -c "set server managers += root@<fully bait hostname>"
```

Configure the Torque server to let the "real" job to use only the others queue. Execute on each of the others queue something like:

```
$> qmgr -c "set queue prod resources_default.neednodes = lcgpro"
$> qmgr -c "set queue cert resources_default.neednodes = lcgpro"
```

10.2.5 REFRESH QUEUE

Set a cron file, called `fix_wnodes_job`, in order to remove job in the HOLD state.

```
$> cat /etc/cron.d/fix_wnodes_job
*/5 * * * root /usr/bin/fix_jobs_mai.sh
```

The `fix_jobs_mai.sh` script is described below:

```
$> cat /usr/local/bin/fix_jobs_mai.sh
#!/bin/bash
for i in `diagnose -q | grep -P -i "Hold|Def" | awk '{print $2}'` \
do
releasehold $i
done
for i in `showq | grep BatchHold | awk '{print $1}'` \
do
releasehold $i
done
```

11 SITE SPECIFIC CONFIGURATION

Each `wnodes_preexec` script has the `/etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf` file as configuration file, whose name and location can be renamed and changed according to the site. In case of LSF this file needs to be copied in the `$(LSF_ENVDIR)/scripts` directory.

The `/etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec.conf` file has an INI format and contains the following information:

```
[general]
TMPFILE=/tmp/my_bait
LOCAL_DOMAIN =<domain name>
NS_HOST=<fully nameserver hostname>
NS_PORT=8219
BAIT_PORT=8111
FAIL_RETURN_STATUS = 1

[default]
TYPE=<type of request>
IMG=<tag name>
NETWORK_TYPE=<type of network>
CPU=1
MEM=2500
STORAGE=30
ENABLEVIRTIO=YES
BANDWIDTH=10
PX_SCRIPT=

[<user_name>|<unix_group_name>]
TYPE=<type of request>
IMG=<tag name>
NETWORK_TYPE=<type of network>
CPU=1
MEM=2700
STORAGE=30
ENABLEVIRTIO=YES
VM_CONFIG_MOUNT_113-MOUNT=ce02-lcg.cr.cnaf.infn.it:/etc/grid-security /etc/grid-security
VM_CONFIG_USELVM_MOUNT=/dev/vdb /mnt
VM_CONFIG_USELVM_LINK=/mnt /tmp
```

where there are at least three sections:

general is the section that contains basic options for the `wnodes_preexec` configuration:

TMPFILE specifies the temporary file created by the `wnodes_preexec` script to provide the bait hostname that is managing the job;

LOCAL_DOMAIN specifies the local domain;

NS_HOST specifies the fully qualified `wnodes_nameserver` hostname;

NS_PORT specifies the port number of the `wnodes_nameserver` service;

BAIT_PORT specifies the port number of the `wnodes_bait` service;

FAIL_RETURN_STATUS represents the failed status returned by the `wnodes_preexec` script. In case of LSF the value is 1, otherwise it is greater than 1.

default is the section that contains default options for a given request received by the `px`:

TYPE is the type of request that the `wnodes_preexec` can support. The possible types are `BATCH`, and `BATCH_REAL`. If it contains `BATCH`, then the request will contain batch jobs. If it contains `BATCH_REAL`, then the request will contain real jobs;

IMG is the unique identifier of the virtual image. It specifies the image that the `px` can request in order to be instantiated by the `wnodes_hypervisor`;

NETWORK_TYPE can be the `OPEN` value or the `CLOSE` value (see table 2);

CPU is the value of the virtual machine `cpu`;

MEM is the value of the virtual machine memory;

STORAGE is the value of the virtual machine storage;

ENABLEVIRTIO specifies if any driver for the interface virtualization is enabled. Its value can be `YES` or `NO`;

BANDWIDTH is the value of the virtual machine bandwidth;

PX_SCRIPT is the `wnodes_preexec` script that is executed on the virtual machine to guarantee some settings like the FS presence.

<user_name> | <unix_group_name> is the section that contains options that identify a type of VM associated to that name. So all the requests coming from the user will have instantiated the same type of VM. However, a user can submit a different request specifying parameters in the batch job script submission.

TYPE is the type of request that the `wnodes_preexec` can support. The possible types are `BATCH`, and `BATCH_REAL`. If it contains `BATCH`, then the request will contain batch jobs. If it contains `BATCH_REAL`, then the request will contain real jobs;

IMG is the unique identifier of the virtual image. It specifies the image that the `px` can request in order to be instantiated by the `wnodes_hypervisor`;

NETWORK_TYPE can be the `OPEN` value or the `CLOSE` value (see table 2);

CPU is the value of the virtual machine `cpu`;

MEM is the value of the virtual machine memory;

STORAGE is the value of the virtual machine storage;

ENABLEVIRTIO specifies if any driver for the interface virtualization is enabled. Its value can be `YES` or `NO`.

BANDWIDTH is the value of the virtual machine bandwidth **TO BE CHECKED**;

VM_CONFIG_MOUNT_113-MOUNT specify that the specified directories will be mounted on the virtual machine;

VM_CONFIG_USELVM_MOUNT specify that the `/dev/vdb` will be mounted on the `/mnt`;

VM_CONFIG_USELVM_LINK specify that the `/dev/vdb` will be linked on the `/mnt`.

In case of PBS set the prologue in all bait nodes as follows:

```
$> cat /var/torque/mom_priv/prologue
#!/bin/bash

while [ ! -f /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec ]; do sleep 3 ; done
sleep 10
/usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec -f /etc/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
--jobid $1 --username $2 &> /root/prologue.txt
$> chmod 500 /var/torque/mom_priv/prologue
$> chmod 500 /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_preexec
```

In case of PBS configure the epilogue in all WN nodes:

```
$> chmod 500 /var/torque/mom_priv/epilogue
$> chmod 500 /usr/bin/wnodes/site_specific/wnodes_postexec
```

12 OCCI SERVER CONFIGURATION

The `wnodes_cloud` component provides Virtual Machines (VM) management by submitting requests through the OCCI interface (version 1.1).

12.1 WNODES CLOUD SETTINGS

The `wnodes_cloud` configuration files that need to be edited are:

- `/etc/wnodes/cloud/application.properties`
- `/etc/wnodes/cloud/extensions.properties`

The file `/etc/wnodes/cloud/application.properties` defines the main settings for the service:

```
#Server key/certificate
socket.sslcert=<host_certificate_path>
socket.sslkey=<host_private_key_path>

#Gridmapfile location
gridmapfile.gridmapfile_path=<path_to_gridmapfile>

#Database configuration
db.connection.name=<WNoDeS Cache Manager database name>
db.connection.username=<database user>
db.connection.password=<database password>

#WNoDes Cache Manager
wn_cm.host=<WNoDeS Cache Manager host>
wn_cm.port=<WNoDeS Cache Manager port>
```

where:

socket.sslcert is the absolute path name of the host certificate for the machine where the `wnodes_cloud` service runs;

socket.sslkey is the absolute path name of the host private key for the machine where the `wnodes_cloud` service runs;

gridmapfile.gridmapfile_path is the absolute path name of the gridmap file used for authenticating users;

db.connection.name is the name of the database the service share with the WNoDeS Cache Manager;

db.connection.username is the name for the user granted to access the database;

wn_cm.host is the name of the host where the WNoDeS Cache Manager runs;

wn_cm.port is the port number where the WNoDeS Cache Manager service listens;

The file `/etc/wnodes/cloud/extensions.properties` defines the operating system name and type of architecture for each of the image tags available:

```
# VM images setup
vmImageConfigurator.vmsetup[<image_tag>]=<OS name>,<arch>,<image_tag>
#Example:
#vmImageConfigurator.vmsetup[wn_sl53_T3]=Scientific Linux 5.8,x86_64,wn_sl53_T3
```

12.2 RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

12.2.1 VIRTUAL MACHINES PRE-DEFINED SIZES

Different sizes in terms of cores, memory and storage can be allocated:

Size tag	Cores	Memory (GB)	Storage (GB)
small	1	1.7	50
medium	2	3.5	100
large	4	7	200
extralarge	8	14	400

If the size tag is not specified in the request, or a wrong one is used, a VM of 'small' type is allocated.

12.2.2 OCCI OPERATIONS

The WNoDeS cloud component provides a subset of the OCCI specification features. All the possible operations allowed on the VM resource type are reported in the following table:

HTTP method	Path	Description
GET	/-/	Returns the OCCI capabilities provided by the service
GET	/compute/	Returns a list of virtual machines belonging to the user
POST	/compute/	Creates a virtual machine. Returns the uuid of the new resource
GET	/compute/[uuid]	Returns details about a specific virtual machine
DELETE	/compute/[uuid]	Destroy a specific virtual machine

12.2.3 VM CREATION

In order to successfully create a new virtual machine, a user must fulfill the following conditions:

- owns a personal X.509 certificate
- belongs to a supported Virtual Organization (VO)

Moreover, to be able to login passwordless to the created machine, the user must provide a valid public ssh key. This can be achieved, for example, simply exporting the content of the public key and then using the new variable when submitting the create request by the command line:

```
export SSHPK=`cat $HOME/.ssh/id_rsa.pub`
```

12.2.4 VM STATUSES

Currently only two OCCl statuses are provided for a VM:

- If WNoDeS is able to allocate the requested VM, the machine status will be displayed as `ACTIVE` and a real hostname will be provided.
- If WNoDeS is not able to allocate the requested VM, the machine status will be displayed as `ACTIVE` but with the hostname set to `Unknown` (creation aborted).
- During the resource allocation process the VM status will be `INACTIVE`.

12.2.5 VM DELETION

Only VMs which status is `ACTIVE` can be destroyed.

12.2.6 USER CREDENTIALS

All the operations could be performed providing both user cert/key or a user proxy.

Proxy version example

```
curl -i -X POST --cacert user_proxy --capath /etc/grid-security/certificates  
--cert user_proxy --key user_proxy
```

Certificate version example

```
curl -i -X POST --capath /etc/grid-security/certificates  
--cert usercert.pem --key userkey.pem
```

12.2.7 EXAMPLES OF USAGE

The following examples will show how to query the OCCl server by using a user certificate:

OCCI Query interface

```
curl -i --capath /etc/grid-security/certificates --cert usercert.pem
--key userkey.pem -H "Accept: text/plain"
https://test-wnodes-web02.cnaf.infn.it:8443/-/
```

CREATE a Virtual Machine

```
curl -i -X POST --capath /etc/grid-security/certificates
--cert usercert.pem --key userkey.pem
-H 'X-Auth-VO: testers.eu-emi.eu'
-H 'X-Ssh-Pk: ssh-rsa AAAAB3NzaC1yc2EAAAABIwAAAQEAqozR72lDn/dwVLyVlRsawArBvXE
u9IOSkd9UgBR7udFMtZXl09bIQIkyb8+RR6N3IiVgtCQ4m7VgZ41W4csfY3ZzZJ5D+AneuQiaHOuc
4u/d1V2+Dwn3F6rRNQlMDC8eijseVPUR3d0oCnhUCqzOpM1H+YhGPz8kURSzttr0Z7USZ2VlnNZvR
sPytXgq1Vb/W+/DOc7qGysdQ7GUN/Cnr1ryxNE9wiRfy8YdxbDA+G70vQBpftOa1a72RHq1VW2w8R
22gzrIfVYTeaZPewzYKRNTC2LzERUBn44fCrME6p/Wfn7siRW5GTARCjlcNGwPn/9CM1HpQ5DCDhT
0JzhQvw== user@test-wnodes-ui.cnaf.infn.it'
-H 'Category: compute; scheme="http://schemas.occi.org/infrastructure#"; class="kind";'
-H 'Content-Type: text/plain'
-H 'Category: small; scheme="http://schemas.wnodes.org/template/resource#"; class="mixin";'
-H 'Category: WeNMR-Demo-INFN; scheme="http://schemas.wnodes.org/template/os#"; class="mixin";'
https://test-wnodes-web02.cnaf.infn.it:8443/compute/
```

GET the list of allocated Virtual Machines

```
curl -i --capath /etc/grid-security/certificates --cert usercert.pem --key userkey.pem
https://test-wnodes-web02.cnaf.infn.it:8443/compute/
```

GET details for an allocated Virtual Machine

```
curl -i --capath /etc/grid-security/certificates --cert usercert.pem
--key userkey.pem
https://test-wnodes-web02.cnaf.infn.it:8443/compute/a518f07e-19d0-4dce-bd04-61af307a82a9
```

DELETE a Virtual Machine

```
curl -i -X DELETE --capath /etc/grid-security/certificates
--cert usercert.pem --key userkey.pem
https://test-wnodes-web02.cnaf.infn.it:8443/compute/a518f07e-19d0-4dce-bd04-61af307a82a9
```

12.2.8 WNoDES OCCI API REFERENCE PAGE

After the `wnodes_cloud` service started, a list of examples for the OCCI API usage is available at the following page:

https://<your_host>:<your_port>/doc/occi_api.html

12.2.9 LOG FILE

The main log file is `/var/log/wnodes/cloud/wnodes_cloud.log`.

13 CACHEMANAGER CONFIGURATION

The `wnodes_cachemanager` configuration files that need to be edited is `/etc/wnodes/cachemanager/wnodes_cm_config.ini`. It has an INI format and contains the following information:

```
[CM_CONF]
CACHE_SIZE = 0
CACHE_REFRESH_INTERVAL = 60.0
DATABASE = mysql://root:WnodesCloudManager@localhost/<password>
MAX_LOG_SIZE = 100000
LOGFILE = wnodes_cachemanager.log
TIMEOUT = 30.0
PORT = 54321

[BATCH_SYS]
TYPE = pbs
USER = cloud
QUEUE = wnodess15

[BAIT_CONF]
PORT = 8111

[NS_CONF]
HOST = test-wnodes07.cnaf.infn.it
PORT = 8219

[WEBAPP_CONF]
HOST = localhost

[DEFAULT_VM_OPTION]
CPU = 1
BANDWIDTH = 10
IMG = wnodes_tw
MEM = 1700
MOUNT =
STORAGE = 50

[KEY_CERT]
CA_CERT = /etc/grid-security/certificates/INFN-CA-2006.pem
CM_PRIVATE_KEY = /root/.ssh/hv_id_rsa
CM_PUBLIC_KEY = /root/.ssh/hv_id_rsa.pub
SERVER_CERT = /etc/grid-security/hostcert.pem
SERVER_KEY = /etc/grid-security/hostkey.pem
```

`CM_CONF` is the name of the section that contains the following options:

CACHE_SIZE specifies the number of virtual machines to handle in cache;

CACHEREFRESH_INTERVAL is the time in seconds to wait during the cache refreshing;

DATABASE specifies the database connection;

MAX_LOG_SIZE specifies the maximum size of the logging filename;

LOGFILE specifies the logging filename;

TIMEOUT is the maximum time in minutes to wait for the vm creation;

PORT is the port number where the `wnodes_cachemanager` service runs.

BATCH_SYS is the name of the section that contains the following options:

TYPE specifies the type of batch system. If it is set to `LSF`, the batch system will be `LSF`. If it is set to `PBS`, the batch system will be `Torque/Maui`;

USER specifies the user with which the job to instantiate the machine is run;

QUEUE specifies the batch system queue configured to submit job.

BAIT_CONF is the name of the section that contains the following options:

PORT is the port number where the `wnodes_cachemanager` service runs.

NS_CONF is the name of the section that contains the following options:

HOST is the fully qualified hostname where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs;

PORT is the port number where the `wnodes_nameserver` service runs.

WEBAPP_CONF is the name of the section that contains the following options:

HOST is the fully qualified hostname where the OCCl server runs.

DEFAULT_VM_OPTION is the name of the section that contains the following options:

IMG is the default value of the virtual machine image;

MEM is the default value of the virtual machine memory;

CPU is the default value of the virtual machine cpu;

BANDWIDTH is the default value of the virtual machine bandwidth;

MOUNT specifies the directories that will be mounted on the virtual machine;

STORAGE is the default value of the virtual machine storage.

KEY_CERT is the name of the section that contains the following options:

CA_CERT specifies the CA file of the OCCl server certificate;

CM_PRIVATE_KEY specifies the private key file, the same of the hypervisors;

CM_PUBLIC_KEY specifies the public key file, the same of the hypervisors;

SERVER_CERT specifies the hostcert file;

SERVER_KEY specifies the hostkey file.

14 ACCOUNTING CONFIGURATION

15 WNODES PROCESSES

15.1 WNODES_NAMESERVER

The `wnodes_nameserver` service delivers the hostnames specified in the given batch system. It starts getting two input arguments:

1. `-d` that is used to start `wnodes_nameserver` as a service.
2. the `/etc/wnodes/nameserver/mac_list.ini` file that contains the list of hostnames that the `wnodes_hypervisor` service associates to the virtual machines. For each hostname the relative mac address is specified.

and using the following command:

```
service wnodes_nameserver start
```

During its execution the `/var/local/wnodes/wnodes_ns_state.ini` file is created. **TO BE MOVED IN `/var/local/wnodes/nameserver/wnodes_ns_state.ini`**

Once having copied your virtual image files in the repository that you have already defined and configured, the `wnodes_nameserver` service will be populated with all the information on the relevant virtual images by doing as follows (as detailed in Section 7):

```
wnodes_manager -a <tag> <location> <path> <arch> <type>
```

15.2 WNODES_HYPERVERSOR

The `wnodes_hypervisor` service starts using the following command:

```
service wnodes_hypervisor start
```

At the start the `wnodes_hypervisor` service performs the following steps to get the state of the network configuration:

1. it discovers the default ethernet that can be `eth0` or `eth1` of the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname;
2. it extracts the IP address of the default ethernet;
3. it creates a default bridge identified with `br.default` to support default VLAN;
4. it associates to the default bridge the IP address of the default ethernet;
5. it modifies the default gateway in order to be the created default bridge.

Doing so the `wnodes_hypervisor` service is able to instantiate virtual machines that belong to the same VLAN of the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname and also to other VLANs. Therefore, to allow the `wnodes_hypervisor` service to instantiate virtual machines that belong to VLANs that are different compared to the VLAN of the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname, the other VLANs need to be configured on the switch and the network configuration of the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname needs to be changed in order to configure a bridge for each new VLAN. Then, if the `wnodes_hypervisor` service receives the request

to instantiate a virtual machine that belongs to a different VLAN, the `wnodes_hypervisor` service will create a dedicated bridge for the VLAN identified with `br.VLAN`, the relative virtual ethernet interface for the VLAN identified with `eth.VLAN` and the link to the bridge.

At the stop of the `wnodes_hypervisor` service, the virtual machines are destroyed but the configuration of the network, which is saved in the `/var/log/wnodes/hypervisor/hv_network_current_status` file at the start of the service, is not canceled.

An example of the `/var/log/wnodes/hypervisor/hv_network_current_status` file that is created by the `wnodes_hypervisor` service when it starts is shown below:

```
#Interface:Type:Status:VLAN:Bridge:Hostname  
  
eth1.default:vlan:UP:default:br.default:localhost  
br.default:bridge:UP:default:br.default:hv-205-06-27-01-b  
  
eth1.208:vlan:UP:208:br.208:hv-205-06-27-01-b  
br.208:bridge:UP:208:br.208:hv-205-06-27-01-b  
  
eth1.216:vlan:UP:216:br.216:hv-205-06-27-01-b  
br.216:bridge:UP:216:br.216:hv-205-06-27-01-b  
  
eth1.nic:UP:default:br.default:hv-205-06-27-01-b  
br.service:bridge:UP:service:br.service:hv-205-06-27-01-b
```

where

Interface is the name of the interface.

Type is the type of the interface.

Status provides the state of the interface.

VLAN provides the name of the VLAN.

Bridge is the link with the bridge.

Hostname provides the hostname of the hypervisor.

Looking at the network configuration file, `eth1` is the default ethernet, for which a default bridge is created. Then further ethernets and bridges are specified for other VLANs such as 208 and 216, because the `wnodes_hypervisor` service needs to instantiate virtual machines that belong to different VLANs compare to the default one.

The `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname has a private network interface. The service bridge allows the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname to have a point to point connection with all the virtual machines it supports. Doing so the virtual machine is able to contact the `wnodes_hypervisor` service by using the private interface of the `wnodes_hypervisor` hostname without accessing the switch.

15.3 WNODES_BAIT

The `wnodes_bait` service starts using the following command:

```
service wnodes_bait start
```

15.4 WNODES_MANAGER

Remember to destroy VM as following:

```
# wnodes_manager -X <VM name>
```